

Preliminary Assessment of the Seismic Hazard for the District of Pathankot (Punjab), India

Short Paper

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ABSTRACT

A preliminary assessment of earthquake hazards for the district of Pathankot (Punjab) has been carried out. The study area has already experienced strong ground motions of intensity VII in the past during the 1905 Kangra earthquake. The epicenter of the 1905 Kangra earthquake was only 60 km away from the study area. Hence, the proximity of the study area to the northwestern Himalayas makes it susceptible to damage due to large earthquakes in the future. Therefore, deterministic seismic hazard analysis (DSHA) has been carried out for the district. For this purpose, earthquake data has been collected from various seismological agencies e.g. NDMA, IMD, ISC-UK, and USGS, and a comprehensive earthquake catalog has been prepared. Several ground motion prediction equations (GMPEs) have been reviewed and analyzed to select a GMPE appropriate for carrying out DSHA. Earthquake hazard parameters have been formulated in terms of peak ground accelerations (PGA). Based on the results, a seismic hazard map for the district has been prepared. The study shows that the region can experience severe strong ground motions originating from northwestern Himalayan earthquakes and hence, structures must be designed based on hazard parameters determined considering the local tectonic setting. The developed hazard map would help engineers and town planners in designing earthquake-resistant structures and retrofitting existing structures.

Keywords: DSHA, Maximum magnitude potential, Peak ground acceleration, Pathankot

INTRODUCTION

Earthquakes are the most hazardous natural events which can inflict massive damage to structures and can wipe out entire cities in minutes. In the past few decades, the earthquakes in India have gone up as the Indian plate and Eurasian plate are bashing at a rate of 50 mm/year (Peltzer and Saucier, 1996). The mighty Himalayas are born due to the clashing of these two plates, which makes the terrain area in the vicinity susceptible to moderate to severe earthquakes. Some of the significant seismic events that occurred in this area are the Uttarkashi earthquake (1991), the Chamoli earthquake (1999), and the Nepal earthquake (2015). The wreckage caused by these earthquakes has been a wake-up call

for the government to take suitable mitigation measures.

Seismic zoning map of India as per BIS-1893: Part-1 (2016) offers a crude idea of the earthquake hazard as it gets updated only after the occurrence of an earthquake. Hence, for an emerging country like India, appropriate steps for seismic hazard assessment are necessary to estimate an optimum and reliable value of possible earthquake ground motion. These prognosticated values could be used as an input to assess the seismic vulnerability of an area, based on which new construction and the restoration works of existing structures can be carried out. The purpose of a seismic hazard analysis (SHA) is to quantify

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potential damage and loss due to future earthquakes. It includes a quantitative evaluation of ground shaking hazards at a particular site. SHA can be used to make regional macro or micro zoning maps which are useful in earthquake-resistant building design and construction, land use planning, emergency plan, and estimation of possible economic loss.

Two perspectives, probabilistic seismic hazard analysis (PSHA) and deterministic seismic hazard analysis (DSHA) are commonly used for seismic hazard assessment. In DSHA, a specific earthquake scenario is assumed based on both historical and instrumental data, and hazard parameters are estimated considering the attenuation characteristics of the region. In this method, the source causing the maximum hazard at any location is considered to be the controlling source that poses a maximum threat to that particular location. Probabilistic seismic hazard analysis (PSHA) is a methodology that considers the uncertainties in size, location, and occurrence of an earthquake, and estimates the likelihood of various levels of earthquake-caused ground motions being exceeded in a given time period at a location. The results of such an analysis are expressed as estimated probabilities per year or estimated annual frequencies.

The results of the seismic hazard analysis are formulated generally in terms of peak ground acceleration (PGA) and spectral acceleration (S_a). Conventionally, PGA is used to quantify ground motion and used to calculate lateral forces and shear stresses in the equivalent-static-force procedures in building codes, and in liquefaction analysis. The S_a is the maximum acceleration experienced by a damped single-degree-of-freedom oscillator and is a crude representation of building response. These parameters are the prime inputs to seismic hazard analysis and hence must be calculated with extreme caution.

In the present study, an attempt has been made to assess seismic hazards for the District of Pathankot in State of Punjab using a deterministic approach. The results of the study would help in the more efficient design of earthquake-resistant structures and the planning of rescue arrangements.

STUDY AREA

Pathankot district is located in the north zone of the State of Punjab (India). The district is spread in an area of 929 km². It is located at the foothills of Shivalik Hills. It shares international borders with the Narowal District of Pakistani Punjab and state borders with the Kathua District of Jammu & Kashmir and Chamba and Kangra districts of Himachal Pradesh. The two main rivers, Beas and Ravi, passes through the district. The Latitude is 32.324276° N and the longitude is 75.59063° E.

The District is only 60 km away from the epicenter of the 1905 Kangra earthquake. The 1905 Kangra earthquake occurred in the Kangra Valley and the Kangra region of the Punjab Province (modern-day Himachal Pradesh) in India on 4th April 1905. The earthquake measured 7.8 on the surface wave magnitude scale and killed more than 20,000 people. Some of the major earthquakes that occurred near the region during the last 200 years are the 1934 Bihar-Nepal earthquake (Mw 8.4), 1950 Assam earthquake (Mw 8.7), 1905 Kangra earthquake (Mw 7.8), 1991 Uttarkashi (Mw 6.8), 1993 Killari earthquake (Mw 6.2), 1999 Chamoli earthquake (Mw 6.8), 2005 Kashmir earthquake (Mw 7.6) and 2015 Gorkha earthquake (Mw 7.8).

An area in 300 km radius around the Pathankot district has been selected as the seismic study region (SSR).

EARTHQUAKE HISTORY OF THE REGION

A comprehensive earthquake catalogue is a prerequisite for earthquake hazard analysis. A reliable seismic hazard assessment for a region strongly depends on the data statistics of the events. There are two types of database available: pre-instrumental and instrumental period database. Records of pre-instrumental events are of immense importance for the compilation of earthquake catalogue. Pre-instrumental data are available for damaging earthquakes and have been collected from catalogue of National Disaster Management Authority of India (NDMA, 2011). The instrumental data have been collected from various national and international seismological agencies such as

National Disaster Management Authority (NDMA), Indian Meteorological Department (IMD), International Seismological Centre (ISC-UK) and United States Geological Survey (USGS). A comprehensive earthquake catalogue has been prepared for a period from 1800 AD to 2017 AD by combining the pre-instrumental and instrumental data collected. The compiled catalogue has the 1256 events of magnitude $M_w \geq 4$ occurred in the seismic study region (between $28^\circ - 33^\circ$ N to $73^\circ - 77^\circ$ E) till December 2017. An Epicenter map has been developed using the prepared catalogue as shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1: Epicentral Map of Study Area

The events in the catalogue have been converted to a common scale of moment magnitude (M_w). For this, numerous empirical relations are available to convert different magnitude scales to moment magnitude (M_w). Pre-instrumental data is usually available on MMI scale and have been converted to moment magnitude (M_w) using the Gutenberg-Richter (1956) relation. The following correlations developed by Scordilis (2006) between $m_b - M_w$ and $M_s - M_w$ have been used. For the conversion of local magnitude (M_L) to moment magnitude (M_w), regional correlation is generally preferred. Hence, the following correlation developed by Kolathayar et al. (2012) for India and adjoining areas has been used. The following correlation developed by Yenier et al. (2008) between $M_d - M_w$ has been used.

SEISMOTECTONICS OF THE REGION

A tectonic map developed for the seismic study region by Puri and Jain (2018) has been used in this study (see Figure 2). The tectonic map was developed using Seismotectonic Atlas of India and its Environs (SEISAT) (Dasgupta et al., 2000). In order to identify the active tectonic sources likely to generate strong ground motions in the study area, the earthquake data from the catalogue have been superimposed on to the tectonic map. A total of 10 tectonic features which are associated with earthquakes of moment magnitude 4.0 and above have been identified as active tectonic sources, out of which 08 sources have been selected as potential seismogenic sources. The values of maximum observed magnitude (M_{obs}) for various seismogenic sources have been reported in Table 1.

Table 1: Maximum Observed Magnitudes for Various Sources

S. No.	Seismogenic Source	M_{obs}
1	Sargodha Lahore Delhi Ridge (SLDR)	6.5
2	Main Boundary Thrust (MBT)	8
3	Main Frontal Thrust (MFT)	5
4	Jwala Mukhi Thrust (JMT)	5.5
5	Main Crustal Thrust (MCT)	7.3
6	Sundar Nagar Fault (SNF)	7
7	Kaurik Fault System (KFS)	6.8
8	Lineament System of SLDR (LSLDR)	6

It has been observed that the district of Pathankot has always been under the threat of big earthquakes due to its proximity with Main Boundary Thrust (MBT) and Main Frontal Thrust (MFT) of Himalayan Thrust System.

ESTIMATION OF MAXIMUM MAGNITUDE POTENTIAL FOR THE STUDY REGION

Damaging earthquakes of magnitude (M_w) of 5 and above have been considered for estimation of maximum magnitude potential (M_{max}). The M_{max} values for the potential seismogenic sources present in the study area have been estimated by adding an increment 0.5 to the respective M_{obs} values (Gupta, 2002). The M_{max} values in terms of moment magnitude estimated for the seismic study area range from 5.5 to 8.5. The M_{max} and total fault lengths (TFL) values for the selected seismogenic sources have been reported Table 2.

Fig. 2: Tectonic setup of the seismic study region

Table 2: Maximum Magnitude Potential for Various Sources

Seismogenic Source	Total Fault Length (TFL) in kms	M_{max}
SLDR	Area Source	7
MBT	825	8.5
MFT	32	5.5
JMT	290	6.0
MCT	769	7.8
SNF	101	7.5
KFS	137	7.3
LSDSR	97	6.5

ESTIMATION OF SEISMIC HAZARD

In this study, a global ground motion prediction equation (GMPE) for shallow crustal earthquakes developed by Graizer and Kalkan (2007) has been used for estimating seismic hazard for the district of Pathankot. For the computation of hazard at a grid point, ground motion parameters have been computed w.r.t various seismogenic sources and the source causing maximum ground motion at the point of interest has been identified. The maximum magnitude potential of that seismogenic source has been considered as the controlling earthquake for the grid point under consideration. The maximum PGA value, i.e. PGA_{max} , for the controlling earthquake at a grid point has been considered to prepare a seismic hazard map of the district. The value of PGA_{max} for all grid points ranges from 0.254g to 1.89g. A deterministic seismic hazard map has been developed for the district using nearest neighbor interpolation technique and is shown in Figure 3.

Fig. 3: Deterministic Seismic Hazard Map for Pathankot

A very high to severe seismic hazard has been observed for the entire district. The expected PGA for north eastern part of Pathankot is as high as 1.89g. It has been observed that the PGA reported for this region in IS:1893-Part 1 (2016) quite underestimates the expected seismic hazard.

LIMITATION OF THE STUDY

The study has following limitations:

1. Seismic hazard maps based on probabilistic approach would give more realistic seismic hazard scenario.
2. Due to preliminary nature of the study, the M_{max} values have been calculated using incremental method only. However, a better assessment can be made using some advanced methods, e.g., Mark (1997), Wells and Coopersmith (1994) and Kijko (2011).
3. The catalogue should be screened for foreshocks and aftershocks (Gardner and Knopoff, 1974) and completion periods of should be determined using CUVI method (Mulargia and Tinti, 1985) and Stepp's (Stepp 1972) methods.
4. The study been carried out for rock sites and hence it is necessary to carry out ground response analysis (e.g. Puri and Jain, 2021) for the sites underlain by soils in order to account for the nonlinearity of soils at severe peak

ground accelerations.

5. A detailed study is required for this region of Punjab so that the hazard parameters given in IS:1893-Part 1 (2016) could be suitably revised.

CONCLUSIONS

In the present study, the seismic hazard analysis using deterministic approach has been carried out for estimating peak ground acceleration (PGA) at rock sites for district of Pathankot. It has been observed that the district is prone to high to severe earthquake ground motions ranging up to 1.89g. Hence, a comprehensive evaluation of earthquake hazard for this region is must. The results of this study would help and motivate engineers and investigators in earthquake resistance design of structures and planning of mitigation measures.

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